

Studies on Nickel(II) Mixed Chelates with 3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-1-Methyltriazene-N-Oxide and Some Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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A number of nickel(II) complexes of the type NiL_2 and NiL_2X_2 , where HL is the ligand and X=pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, quinoline and isoquinoline have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature, reflectance spectral data in the solid state, electronic spectral data in solution and infrared spectral studies. A six coordinated *trans*-pseudooctahedral configuration has been suggested for all the mixed ligand nickel complexes prepared.

SIGNIFICANT studies on the structures of simple nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of triazene-N-oxides, formerly known as N-hydroxytriazenes have recently been done by Chakravorty *et al*¹. A distorted octahedral and square planar stereochemistry of the nickel(II) mixed ligand complexes and nickel(II) chelate respectively have been predicted in this paper.

Experimental

Preparation of the reagent : The reagent 3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide was prepared by diazotising *p*-aminoacetophenone and coupling with methylhydroxylamine following the procedure described for its *ortho* isomer².

Preparation of the complexes :

Bis-3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide Ni(II) : $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (A. R.) (0.004 mole) was dissolved in 200-250 ml of distilled water acidified with a few drops of dil. hydrochloric acid. Ethanolic reagent solution (0.01-0.015 mole) was added to the hot aqueous nickel(II) solution with stirring. The greenish yellow complex that formed in the pH range 7.0-7.5 (adjusted with dil. ammonia solution) was filtered hot after digestion on boiling water-bath for 30 min. The complex $Ni(C_9H_{10}O_2N_3)_2$ was washed with hot distilled water and dried at 110-120°.

Dipyridine-bis-3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide Ni(II) : The reagent (0.01-0.02 mole) in ethanol and pyridine (excess) were successively added to a hot ethanolic solution of $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.004 mole) with stirring. The mixture was digested on water-bath (10-20 mins) and then kept at room temperature. The buff coloured complex crystals were suction filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

The compounds Di- β -picoline *bis*-3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide-Ni(II), Di- γ -picoline *bis*-3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide-Ni(II), Di-quinoline *bis*-3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide-Ni(II) and Di-isoquinoline *bis*-3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide-Ni(II) were prepared in an identical manner as described for NiL_2Py_2 complex using β and γ picolines, quinoline and isoquinoline in place of pyridine. The colours of the complexes $NiL_2(\beta\text{-pic})_2$, $NiL_2(\gamma\text{-pic})_2$, NiL_2Q_2 and $NiL_2(IQ)_2$ were cherry red, buff, greenish brown and brown respectively.

Analysis : The respective metal content of the complexes was determined by the usual DMG method after decomposing each of them with a mixture of nitric, sulphuric and perchloric acid. Nitrogen was determined by Duma's method. Since the triazene complexes usually explode at their decomposition temperature, analysis of carbon and hydrogen were not attempted. The analytical results are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements : The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were determined by Guoy's balance using mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as the standard.

Visible absorption spectra : Spectromom 204 spectrophotometer (range 200-1400 nm) was used to record the visible absorption spectra of the complexes with glass cell of 1 cm path.

Reflectance spectra : Spectrophotometer VSU-2P was used to record the spectra of the complexes using magnesium oxide as the standard.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectra of the complexes in the solid state were recorded by Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrophotometers 137, 177 and 298.

The visible absorption spectra in methanol and reflectance spectra of the mixed ligand complexes

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND OTHER PROPERTIES OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES WITH 3-(*p*-ACETOPHENYL)-1-METHYL-TRIAZENE-N-OXIDE AND OTHER NITROGEN DONOR LIGANDS

Compound with colour	Decomposition temperature (°C)	%Ni Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	%Weight loss Found at 170° (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ Py ₂]	218	9.75 (9.77)	18.50 (18.63)	26.75 (26.28)	3.15
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (β -pic) ₂]	226	9.38 (9.33)	17.62 (17.80)	29.70 (29.56)	3.17
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	230	9.85 (9.33)	17.90 (17.80)	29.34 (29.56)	3.08
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (quinoline) ₂]	220	8.38 (8.37)	15.80 (15.98)	36.72 (36.90)	3.13
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (isoquinoline) ₂]	224	8.25 (8.37)	15.82 (15.92)	36.75 (36.80)	3.15
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂]	235	13.34 (13.25)	18.86 (18.96)	—	diamagnetic

are given in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively. The ir spectra of the ligand and complexes have been interpreted in the discussion.

 TABLE 2—ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES WITH 3-(*p*-ACETOPHENYL)-1-METHYL-TRIAZENE-N-OXIDE AND OTHER NITROGEN DONOR LIGANDS IN METHANOL

Complex	Colour of the solution	Absorption maxima nm	Absorption maxima cm ⁻¹ (molar)
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ Py ₂]	Yellow	410 670 dou- 707 blet 950 wsh 1110	24390 (2350) 16129(32.5) 14285(31.2) 10526(21.8) 9009(21.8)
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (β -pic) ₂]	Yellow	405 720 br 1110	24690(2000) 19888(23.8) 9009(21.8)
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	Yellow	410 710 br 1105	24390(2125) 14085(26.2) 9050(22.6)
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ -(quinoline) ₂]	Yellow	410 700 br 920 sh 1135	24390(2185) 14285(28.8) 10870(20.2) 8888(22.5)
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ -(isoquinoline) ₂]	Yellow	410 7700 br 900 wsh 1100	24390(2180) 14285(27.5) 11111(21.8) 9030(23.2)
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂]	Yellow	400 700 1075	25000(2375) 14285(44.4) 9302(31.2)

wsh : weak shoulder, br : broad, sh : shoulder.

Results and Discussion

The slightly lower magnetic moments of the mixed ligand complexes compared to the usual octahedral Ni(II) complexes³ (2.83-3.4 B.M.) may be due to the increased axial distortion leading to distorted octahedral structures. A square planar geometry for NiR₂ was suggested on the ground of its diamagnetic property.

The two principal crystal field bands in the regions 10638-11111 cm⁻¹ and 17857-18518 cm⁻¹ of the nickel(II) complexes I-V represented in Table 3

 TABLE 3—REFLECTANCE SPECTRAL DATA OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES WITH 3-(*p*-ACETOPHENYL)-1-METHYL-TRIAZENE-N-OXIDE AND OTHER NITROGEN DONOR LIGANDS

Complex	Absorption maxima	
	nm	cm ⁻¹
I [Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ Py ₂]	410, 545 br	24990, 18348
II [Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (β -pic) ₂]	740 wsh, 875 wsh	13513, 10869
	400, 560 br, 900	25000, 17857, 11111
III [Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	400, 540 br, 900	25000, 18518, 11111
	IV [Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ -(quinoline) ₂]	410, 560 br
730 wsh, 925		13698, 10810
V [Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ -(isoquinoline) ₂]	405, 550 br	24690, 18181
	750 wsh, 940	13333, 10638
VI [Ni(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃) ₂]	390, 550, 675 wsh	25640, 18181, 14814

br=broad, wsh=weak shoulder.

may be attributed to the first (ν_1) and second (ν_2) transitions. These two transitions are assigned $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{2g}(F)$ and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$ respectively. In NiR₂Py₂, NiR₂Q₂ and NiR₂(IQ)₂ complexes one additional band appeared in each case in the region 13333-13698 cm⁻¹. This is probably due to spin forbidden $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 1B_g(D)$ transition. The strong intense bands occurring in the region 24390-25640 cm⁻¹ of these complexes are attributed to charge transfer bands. The position of the ν_1 and ν_2 bands and their ratio ν_2/ν_1 (1.6-1.7) clearly point to their distorted octahedral geometry⁴. The strong crystal field band in the complex NiR₂ in the region 18181 cm⁻¹ with weak shoulder in the longer wavelength region has been assigned $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1A_{2g}$ transition and consequently a square planar geometry was proposed for this complex⁵.

The absorption spectra of the nickel(II) complexes taken in methanol signified no change in stereochemistry due to dissolution. The main difference between the electronic absorption spectra of the complexes NiR₂Py₂, NiR₂(β -pic)₂, NiR₂(γ -pic)₂, NiR₂Q₂ and NiR₂(IQ)₂ from that of their corresponding reflectance spectra is that d-d band positions are shifted to longer wavelength regions which may be due to the solvolytic effect of methanol on the ligand molecules

bonded to the metal ion. The increased molar extinction coefficient values of these complexes in solution compared to those of the usual pseudo-octahedral complexes⁶ may be due to the fact that the nitrogen donor molecules which are likely to occupy the *trans* position in the octahedra in the solid state become *cis* in respect of each other in solution resulting in a structure devoid of centre of symmetry (Fig. 1).

chelating agent using N-oxide oxygen atom and secondary amino nitrogen atom as the bonding sites. From the above evidences it is most probable that the actual structures of the nickel(II) mixed ligand complexes are that of distorted octahedron with a prediction that the two further nitrogen donor molecules are located in the *trans* positions in the solid state while on dissolution of the complexes in methanol the two ambidentate ligands

Fig. 1. (X=Py, β -pic, γ -pic, Quinoline and isoquinoline).

The electronic spectral data (absorption maxima at 400, 700 and 1075) of diamagnetic NiR_2 complex in methanol indicate a structural change of the complex in going from solid to solution state. The solid state spectral data support a square planar environment in this complex while in methanol solution the spectral data point to the typical distorted hexacoordinated nickel(II). Such changes may probably be due to the solvation of the complex whereby the solvent molecules possibly get coordinated at 5th and 6th positions in square planar structure leading to octahedral geometry.

The N-H band frequency around 3210 cm^{-1} and N-O stretch at 988 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum of the free ligand disappeared and shifted to lower frequency in the spectra of the chelate NiR_2 and all the mixed ligand complexes. The carbonyl stretching frequency at 1670 cm^{-1} of the free ligand remains unaltered in the complexes indicating noninvolvement of the $>C=O$ group in coordination due to spatial disposition. Thus, the ligand triazene-N-oxide functions as a bidentate

chelating agent using N-oxide oxygen atom and secondary amino nitrogen atom as the bonding sites. From the above evidences it is most probable that the actual structures of the nickel(II) mixed ligand complexes are that of distorted octahedron with a prediction that the two further nitrogen donor molecules are located in the *trans* positions in the solid state while on dissolution of the complexes in methanol the two ambidentate ligands

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